

COMPARATIVE STUDY OF FIXED TIME ARTIFICIAL INSEMINATION AND CONVENTIONAL PROTOCOLS IN RJM CATTLE FARM, SAN FELIPE, ZAMBALES

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Abstract

Beef cattle production is a promising livelihood for local farmers, coupled with the use of artificial insemination hastening the population of genetically superior cattle. The farm is suitable for raising improved cattle breeds and adapted to local conditions. Artificial insemination requires the skill of the technician, posing a factor in the failure and success rate of pregnancy. It compares the conventional treatment and fixed-time artificial insemination using different drug combinations. The combination of controlled internal release drug with human chorionic gonadotropins effectively increased the pregnancy rate of the cows treated using fixed-time artificial insemination compared to conventional artificial insemination. It effectively surpassed the conventional treatment by at least 6% in inducing estrus while the pregnancy rate increased by at least 16% in beef cattle production. The protocol may further be studied in other climate-type environments and provinces to validate the efficacy of the result.

INTRODUCTION

Artificial insemination (AI) has been the major breeding tool for expanding the usage of superior genetics of paternal origin. Currently, it is the widely used breeding technique in the country, but there is a need to improve its efficiency. One of the extensively used and effective reproductive biotechnologies in livestock breeding is Fixed Time Artificial Insemination (FTAI), which facilitates induced ovulation and more precise/fixed timing of insemination without the need for detection of estrus.

Artificial insemination (AI) was the common practice of improving the genetics of dairy and beef cattle in the country using locally produced or imported frozen semen (Atabay et al., 2019) and an effective method to reproduce domestic and non-domestic animals (Babera and Mingala, 2015).

Furthermore, FTAI has been initiated in the Philippines using dairy buffaloes as part of the intensified reproductive management program developed for this species mainly to address concerns on poor and more elusive behavioral estrus, asynchrony in ovulation and insemination time which results in poor AI outcome. Its initial implementation at Philippine Carabao Center's institutional herd resulted in an improved conception rate and is gaining ground in its widespread application in livestock.

While the focus during its earlier implementation was achieving precise timing for AI, other opportunities/aspects have been unfolded and realized during its execution which can further improve FTAI efficiency (Atabay et al., 2019).

Since Philippines was one of the countries worldwide with a low rate of pregnancy in calves, normally, AI was performed in animals with natural estrus. Following the system, the number of animals inseminated at a given time was limited resulting to slow calf production. In some instances, the AI technology was being done in combination with estrus synchronization to increase the number of animals inseminated at a given time, however the percent conception rate is very low compared to what is being expected (Atabay et al., 2019).

Nowadays, timed artificial insemination is being undertaken to program the herd to calve almost at a given time for easier and efficient herd management program implementation. Moreover, considering the positive findings of fixed time artificial insemination in water buffaloes, results of the proposed research study was useful in improving the beef cattle industry and the livestock in the country in general (Ferrer et al., 2021).

Therefore, the significance of this study for the farmers is that this research could assist farmers in determining the optimal time for insemination, reducing the time and effort required for reproduction. In the livestock industry, this research could help the cattle industry because this can assist enhanced reproductive efficiency of breeding programs, resulting in improved production and economic benefits. For the future scientists, this study could be used as a reference by future researchers as more literature for the study's progress (Ferrer et al., 2021).

Objectives

Generally, this study aimed to compare the fixed time artificial insemination and conventional protocols' percent pregnancy in beef cattle breeds (*Bos indicus*).

Specifically, the study aims to:

1. Determine the estrus rate of artificially inseminated beef cattle particularly Brahman and Indo-Brahman breeds with basic estrus synchronization and after fixed time artificial insemination protocols.
2. Determine the percent pregnancy among the treatments.

METHODOLOGY

At least ninety (90) beef cattle cows with a body condition score (BCS) of 3 and above and at least one (1) ovary that was ≥ 2 cm in length or width were selected and used in the study. Materials that were used are the following, which included Pfizer EAZI-Breed, Cystorelin, PGF2 α , chorionic gonadotropin, gloves, surgical scissors, a syringe, a semen tank, an electric kettle, an AI gun, a disposable AI gun casing, and an ultrasound scanner. It was a Completely Randomized Design (CRD) study with three (3) different treatments, three (3) replications, and ten (10) samples of animals from each treatment and replication, for a total of 90 animals used in the study. We tested the three treatment groups using FTAI and conventional AI protocols.

Treatment 1. Basic Estrus Synchronization– Control (PGF2a)

All selected open cows were subjected to fixed time artificial insemination following the procedure of Atabay et al., (2019) with some modification. Briefly on Day 0, all selected available animals were subjected to intramuscular injection of 2 ml prostaglandin. On Day 3 all animals were artificially inseminated twice, the first was in the morning and the second was 8 hours after the 1st fixed time artificial insemination. Table 1 presents the schedule of activity for Treatment 1.

Table 1: Schedule of Activity for Treatment 1

Day	Activity
0	PGF ₂ α injection if CL is present
3	1 st AI and follow up insemination 8hr after 1 st AI

Treatment 2. Controlled Internal Drug Release- Gonadotropin-Releasing Hormone (CIDR-GnRH) Protocol

Selected cows were subjected to controlled internal drug release gonadotropin releasing hormone. Briefly, on Day 0, Internal Drug Release (CIDR, 1.38 gms. of micronized natural progesterone, Pfizer EAZI-Breed) was inserted into the vagina and 2 ml gonadotrophin releasing hormone (GnRH, Cystorelin, 100 ug IM) was administered intramuscularly. On Day 7, CIDR was removed and then followed by an intramuscular injection of 2 ml prostaglandin. On Day 9, fifty percent (50%) of the CIDR treated animals was injected with 2nd dose of 2 ml gonadotropin releasing hormone (GnRH, Cystorelin, 100 ug IM) and AI has been done to all animals on Day 10. The experimental treatment design was followed in Table 2 below.

Table 2: Schedule of application for Treatment 2.

Day	Activity
0	CIDR insertion and 1 st GnRH injection
7	CIDR removal and PGF ₂ α injection
9	GnRH injection
10	AI at 14-16 hour after GnRH injection

Treatment 3. Controlled Internal Drug Release- Human Chorionic Gonadotropin (CIDR- hCG) Protocol

The remaining 50% selected cows are subjected to CIDR + human Chorionic Gonadotropin. Briefly, on Day 0, Internal Drug Release (CIDR, 1.38g of micronized natural progesterone, Pfizer EAZI-Breed, was introduced into the vagina, and 2 ml of gonadotrophin-releasing hormone (GnRH, Cystorelin, 100 ug IM) have been given intramuscularly. On Day 7, CIDR was removed, followed by an intramuscular injection of 2 ml of prostaglandin. On Day 10, selected cows are injected with 2ml human chorionic gonadotropin (hCG, Chorulon, 10,000 units IM) intramuscularly at the 1st AI on day 10 (T3-CIDR-hCG). Follow-up has been done at 8 hr after the 1st AI. The experimental treatment design is presented below in Table 3.

Table 3: Schedule of activity for Treatment 3

Day	Activity
0	CIDR insertion and 1 st GnRH injection
7	CIDR removal and PGF2 α injection
10	1 st AI + hCG injection

CIDR-GnRH Protocol

Physiological Events: Day 0: Injection of GnRH induced release of LH from the pituitary causing ovulation of the dominant follicle. CIDR increased circulating level of progesterone which reduced hormonal support for developing follicles that do not respond to GnRH. Both treatments lead to emergence of follicular waves. Days 2-3: A new follicular wave emerged. Days 5-6: Emergence of a dominant follicle. Day 7: PG induced luteolysis of the existing corpus luteum (CL). Concurrent removal of CIDR results in a sudden drop of circulating P4. This hindered the feedback effects on the hypothalamus. GnRH or hCG acts to increase the size of the dominant follicle in the pre-ovulatory period, resulted in a larger oocyte at ovulation and improvement in the subsequent CL. Day 9: Administered in the absence of circulating P4 induced a surge of LH from the anterior pituitary leading to ovulation of the dominant follicle. Day 10: FTAI was performed 14-18 hrs. after GnRH injection and hCG at 1st AI. FTAI before ovulation allowed time for sperm capacitation and movement to oviduct.

Animal Selection and Determination of Body Condition Score

Beef cattle, specifically Brahman and Indo-Brahman breeds of at least no less than 60 days postpartum, with a body condition score (BCS) of not less than three (3) and at least one (1) of the ovaries equal to or greater than two (2) cm in length or width, were selected and used in the study. The Philippine Carabao Center's well-trained AI technicians evaluated the BCS (Anon, 1994). A BCS of 1 means the animal is very skinny; a BCS of 2 means the backbone, hips, and shoulder bones can be seen, and the body outline is bony; a BCS of 3 means the ribs are mostly hidden by fat, and the body outline is almost smooth; a BCS of 4 means the animal is smooth, round, and well covered, but there are no obvious fat deposits; and a BCS of 5 means there is a lot of fat on the tail head and brisket, and the dorsal spines, ribs, hooks, and pins are completely covered and can't be felt even when pressing hard.

Estrus Detection and Artificial Insemination

Manifestation of estrus was noted at the time of insemination on Day 10, and follow-up insemination has been done 8 hrs. after the first insemination with frozen-thawed cattle semen derived from bulls with proven fertility. Artificial insemination was done by selected AI technicians of the Philippine Carabao Center. The selection of AI technician was based on his performances for the last 4 years of insemination. The presence of mucus discharge and tonicity of the uterine horn was determined and recorded at the time of artificial insemination. Furthermore, the determination of estrus value was based on the experimental animals that had been used; the total number of animals that showed estrus signs like mounting, increased restlessness and bawling, increased interaction with other cows, and clear mucus discharged from the vulva was observed.

Pregnancy Diagnosis (Transrectal Ultrasonography)

Confirmation of pregnancy was done by ultrasonography on Day 50-60 post AI. We used a transrectal ultrasound scanner (Honda, HS-1600V, Japan) with a 7.5 MHz linear array transducer that was made to be put inside the rectum to do the scans (Mehrajuddin and Derashri, 2013). We scanned the dorsal and lateral surfaces of the uterine horns. We determined the pregnancy status using the modified criteria described by Fricke et al. (2016). Briefly, the criteria included the presence of CL, uterine fluid, and embryo. Cows are considered pregnant when CL is present, there is uterine fluid, and there is an embryo.

Statistical Analysis

One-way ANOVA (GLM procedure, SAS 9.4, Institute Inc., Cary, NC) was used to test differences in the average percent of estrus and the average percent of pregnancy. All data were analyzed and interpreted.

Data Gathering

The percentage of estrous was computed using the formula: number of animals showed signs of estrous at the time of insemination/total number of animals per replication and multiplied by 100. Data were recorded at the time of insemination on Day 10 and the follow-up insemination after 8 hours using the frozen-thawed cattle semen from the selected proven bull of excellent fertility.

The percent pregnancy rate at 60 days post-FTAI was determined by a certified AI technician from the center. The formula used to determine the results was the number of confirmed pregnant cows divided by the total number of animals impregnated, then multiplied by 100.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The average percentage of estrus were computed using the formula of the number of animals that showed signs of estrus at the time of insemination/total number of animals per replication and multiplied by 100. Results are shown below in Table 4.

Table 4: Average percentage of estrus of sample animals

Treatment	R1	R2	R3	Total	Mean
1 (PGF2 α + hCG)	80	80	90	260	86.67
2 (CIDR-Synch + GnRH)	90	90	100	280	93.33
3 (CIDR-Synch + hCG)	90	100	90	280	93.33

Based on the result, Treatment 2 and Treatment 3 obtained the highest mean of 93.33% followed by Treatment 1, with a mean of 86.67%. The one-way analysis of variance of the percentage of estrus revealed that there was no significant difference among treatments because the F value of 1.33 which was 0.3318, was higher than the 0.05 probability level.

The preceding result was supported by a related study of Karsavuranoğlu et al. (2022) on their study wherein they have examined the impact of GnRH injection alone during AI or in association with hCG 5 days after GnRH injection on conception rates in postpartum dairy

cows and resulted that the use of GnRH alone at the time of AI and alongside with hCG on the fifth day following AI, has improved the pregnancy rates in dairy cows between 70 and 120 days postpartum. Nevertheless, there was no difference in pregnancy rates between those two treatments.

On the other hand, another related study of Gridelet et al. (2020) supported this result which stated that, hCG played a role in a variety of processes that ensure the smooth progression of a pregnancy, including the recognition of the pregnancy by the maternal organism, the maintenance of the corpus luteum, the stimulation of progesterone production, the strengthening of embryo implantation, angiogenesis and vasculogenesis required for placental development, control of trophoblast differentiation, and immune regulation at the maternal/fetal interface.

The average percentage of pregnancies were computed using the formula of the number of confirmed pregnant animals/total number of animals per replication and multiplied by 100. Results was presented in Table 5.

Table 5: Average Percentage of Pregnancy

Treatment	R1	R2	R3	Total	Mean
1 (PGF2 α + hCG)	30	40	40	110	36.67b
2 (CIDR-Synch + GnRH)	40	40	50	130	43.33ab
3 (CIDR-Synch + hCG)	50	50	60	160	53.33a

Note: Means with the same letter are not significantly different.

Based on the result, Treatment 3 obtained the highest mean of 53.33% followed by Treatment 2 at mean of 43.33% and the least was Treatment 1 at 36.67%.

This result is supported by a related study of Côrtes et al. (2021) wherein exogenous hCG injection was studied for its impact on ovarian function and pregnancy rates in estrous-induced dairy goats as they transitioned into the breeding season and they have concluded that a single dose of hCG on D7 after estrus reduced the number of medium-sized antral follicles in gestating hCG-treated does, induced the formation of ALSs in ~47% of all hCG-treated does, and significantly increased the pregnancy rate in estrous-induced Toggenburg goats during the breeding season.

Moreover, Smitz and Platteau (2020) stated that over the last few decades, several studies have produced evidence supporting the use of hCG for OS in ART. Indeed, the data showed that hCG plays an essential role in folliculogenesis, improves endometrial receptivity, and is associated with superior embryo quality, all while maintaining a favorable safety profile. These findings support the growing use of hCG as a means of providing LH bioactivity during OS.

The analysis of variance of the percentage of pregnancy revealed that there was no significant difference between treatments due to the F value of 6.33 which was 0.0332, higher than the 0.05 probability level.

Treatment 1 and Treatment 2 were not significantly different with a mean of 36.67 and 43.33 respectively. The same in Treatment 2 and Treatment 3 with the means of 43.33 and 53.33 were

not significant respectively. However, between Treatment 1 and Treatment 3 found a significant difference of means of 36.67 and 53.33 respectively.

In Treatment 3 (CIDR-Synch + hcg) obtained the highest mean of 53.33%, therefore this treatment is deemed to be effective. In fact, Kuru et al. (2017) stated that hCG is administered directly to cows and heifers and has an impact on the ovaries. In their Co-Synch protocol for heifers, Schmitt et al. employed hCG to stimulate ovulation and achieved a 52.9% pregnancy rate. According to the findings, utilizing hCG as the first step in the 5-day Co-Synch approach could be a feasible alternative to GnRH for inducing ovulation. Following ovulation induction with hCG, Groups GPH and PH had 53.2% and 45.9% pregnancy rates, respectively.

Furthermore, another related study of Rizwan et al. (2018) stated that hCG promotes auxiliary corpus luteum in 86% of cows and raises blood P4 concentrations by 4 mg/mL (Wiltbank et al., 2012). This would allow farmers to operate a program in which animals produce offspring more frequently, resulting in higher and longer-term economic benefits.

CONCLUSIONS

Based on the results, the combination of Controlled Internal Drug Release Synch + human Chorionic Gonadotropin performed significantly and effectively for fixed time artificial insemination compared to conventional protocol for beef cattle production. It effectively surpassed the conventional treatment by at least 6% in inducing estrus while the pregnancy rate increased by at least 16% in beef cattle production. Therefore, the use of combination of drugs given could increase beef cattle production through artificial insemination.

Recommendations

The use of combination drug is further recommended to be used in other farm for beef cattle production. Furthermore, the protocol can be tested on the different climatic type within the region and to other provinces. Determine the cost and expense in using the protocol.

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